

DEVELOPMENT OF METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES BY FIBRE COATING AND HIPING

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ABSTRACT

The development of metal matrix composites (MMC) for high-temperature applications is discussed. As processing method fibre coating with matrix and consolidation by hot isostatic pressing (HIPing) is applied. The fibres are coated with matrix by magnetron sputtering. As matrices the titanium alloys IMI834, super α_2 and γ -TiAl with 2 % Nb and 2 % Cr are used. Methods of MMC-consolidation at reduced temperatures are discussed. The consolidation of the SiC- γ -TiAl composites can be improved by using a three coating system of IMI834- γ -TiAl - IMI834. An additional graded titanium boride fibre protecting coating is applied to increase the thermal stability of the fibre-matrix interface. The microstructure and the tensile properties of the as-processed composites and of the composites thermally treated at 800°C/500h are discussed.

INTRODUCTION

Titanium matrix composites (TMC) are characterized by a high specific strength and stiffness [1-3], high fatigue crack growth resistance [4] and very good creep and large stress rupture lives [5,6]. For TMC application temperatures higher than 400°C, a matrix with sufficiently high ductility at room temperature and sufficiently high strength at application temperature has to be found and the problem of fibre matrix interaction has to be solved, however. In the present paper, the MMC microstructure design is discussed with the aim to develop composites suitable for high-temperature applications. As processing method the fibre coating with matrix and consolidation by HIPing is used [1-3, 7].

EXPERIMENTAL

Fibres are coated with matrix using a magnetron sputtering equipment with two pairs of magnetrons, Fig. 1. On a cylindrical fibre holder [8] with the dimensions of 40 cm in diameter and 30 cm in height 150 m of SiC fibres are wound. During the deposition of the matrix the fibre holder rotates about its cylinder axis. For coating the SiC-SCS-6 fibres with matrix of a thickness of 30 μ m between 4h and 8 h of deposition time is used, depending on the applied magnetron power supply between 2 and 4 kW. The coated fibres are introduced into a tube made from matrix material, encapsulated in a stainless steel capsule, outgassed at 450°C/5h, closed by welding and hot isostatically pressed at 190 MPa. The processing temperature was in the range between 870°C and 1000°C, the HIPing was performed during 1/2 and a few hours. From the HIPed material cylindrical samples are machined with a testing length of 30 mm and a diameter of 3.5 mm. Details of sample processing are described

in [1-3]. In the present study, the titanium alloys IMI834, the super α_2 and the γ -TiAl with 2 %Nb and 2 % Cr were used as matrix materials. The IMI834 and the super α_2 were deposited on the fibres by using targets machined from the alloys. For the deposition of γ -TiAl-alloy targets produced from pure elements were used [20]: Cylinders made of pure aluminium, chromium und niobium were inserted into a pure titanium target. The volume content of the pure elements in the target was determined experimentally according to the requirements of the concentration of the elements in the γ -TiAl-matrix.

Fig.1 Equipment with two magnetron pairs A and B for fibre coating with matrix and for the deposition of an additional fibre protecting coating.

RESULTS

There are some advantages of the magnetron sputtering for fibre coating compared with other deposition methods, as e.g. EB-PVD or plasma spraying [3]. Using magnetron sputtering for fibre coating, a grain size of the matrix lower than $1 \mu\text{m}$ is obtained. The chemical element concentration is, with some few exceptions, the same in the coating as in the target material (an exception is Sn in the IMI834, in which 3 wt.% instead of 4.5 wt% is realized, which however can be corrected using an addition of pure element material). A homogeneous coating thickness on the fibre is realized using a pair of magnetrons. The homogeneous coating thickness results in a homogeneous fibre distance distribution in the composites [1-3]. An earlier reported problem of an introduction of oxygen into the matrix using magnetron sputtering was solved in the meantime. The oxygen content in the IMI834- and in the γ -TiAl- alloy used in this paper was 700 wppm and 500 wppm, respectively. Only the composites with the super α_2 , which were processed earlier (1993), contain a high oxygen concentration of 3000 wppm.

COMPOSITE CONSOLIDATION

The consolidation behaviour of composites with the super α_2 as matrix is demonstrated in Fig.2. Before HIPing voids and imperfections are present in the sample, Fig.2a, which are closed during HIP-consolidation by the matrix, as can be seen in Fig.2b. For composites with the super α_2 as matrix an optimization of the HIPing conditions was performed experimentally and as the lowest possible HIPing temperature 870°C was determined. After a HIPing time of 0.5h only small voids remain in the composite between the fibres and the matrix tube material, as can be seen in Fig.3c.

Fig.2. Consolidation of composites with the super α_2 as matrix, a) before HIPing, b) after HIPing at 190 MPa/1000°C/0.5h, c) after HIPing at 190MPa/870°C/0.5h.

Low consolidation temperatures are important in particular for composites with γ -TiAl-alloys as matrix. Due to the small grain size of the matrix material sputtered on the fibres, for the γ -TiAl consolidation temperatures below 1000°C were obtained, Fig.3c. The consolidation temperature can be further decreased when a thin layer of a ductile material is used on the fibres as a "consolidation aid". The fibres were first coated by a thin layer (1 to 2 μm) of the IMI834 alloy, then by a thick layer of γ -TiAl (25 μm) and again with a thin layer of IMI 834, Fig.3a. After a consolidation at 930°C/1h/190MPa, pores observed at 950°C/1h/190 MPa in a composite with the pure γ -TiAl, Fig.3c, are filled by the ductile IMI834-alloy, Fig.3b. The second advantage of the additional ductile layers of IMI834 is the reduction of the sensitivity to crack formation in SiC- γ -TiAl composites. The crack formation can be completely prevented using a three coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl - IMI834. This is demonstrated in Fig.4 where two composites are shown processed at the same HIPing conditions. In the composite processed with the γ -TiAl-alloy many cracks develop during cooling after processing, Fig.4a, while in the composite processed using the coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl -IMI834 no cracks are detected, Fig.4b. The structures surrounding the coated fibres in Fig.4b are the remnants of the IMI834- coating, as can be seen at higher magnification in Fig.3b.

DEVELOPMENT OF NEW FIBRE PROTECTING COATINGS

The presently available fibres (Textron SCS-6^R and British Petroleum SM 1140^{+R}) with a carbon coating are thermally stable in a titanium matrix up to temperatures of 600°C [9]. For application temperatures higher than 600°C an additional coating is needed. Different materials are discussed as possible diffusion and reaction barriers for TMC: TiC, TaC, TiB₂ [10], Y₂O₃ [11] and others. The company British Petroleum has developed a commercial fibre with TiB₂ as an additional coating (BP SM 1240^R). During processing of TMC's with the BP1240-fibres, the TiB₂ reacts with the titanium matrix forming TiB [12], however. The formation of the reaction zone in Ti- SM1240-composites causes a degradation of the composite strength in longitudinal fibre direction [10]. The TiB₂ is, on the other hand, a suitable material for an additional protecting coating in TMC's from the thermodynamical point of view due to its high chemical stability, low solubility of B in titanium and low diffusion rates of B in TiB₂ and in titanium [13]. In a thermodynamic assessment it was predicted [13] that a coating system of TiB_{1.9} - TiB_{0.88} with high concentrations of boron near the carbon coating and a high concentration of titanium near the titanium alloy should result in a high thermal

stability of the fibre-matrix interface in TMC's. This kind of graded titanium boride coating is not realized in the BP 1240-fibre (The gradient is reverse to that proposed by [13],[14]).

Fig.3. Application of a three coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl- IMI834 for the consolidation of composites with the γ -TiAl as matrix, a) coated monofilament, b) consolidation of the composite with the three coating system at 930°C/1h/190MPa, c) consolidation of the composite with the γ -TiAl at 950°C/1h/190MPa.

Fig.4a. Crack formation in composites with the γ -TiAl as matrix during cooling down after processing, b) The crack formation can be prevented by using a coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl- IMI834.

Using our equipment with two magnetron pairs, a graded titanium boride coating was deposited on SCS-6-fibres [14]. In the equipment shown in Fig. 1 magnetron pair A was supplied with TiB_2 targets and the pair B with pure titanium targets. For the deposition of TiB_2 a constant power supply of

2 kW was used. The power supply of the pure titanium targets was varied. The Ti deposition was performed with an increasing deposition rate, beginning from zero. The increase rate of the deposition power for the Ti-magnetrons was chosen to give Ti-concentrations which fulfill the requirements of the thermodynamic assessment of [13] (details in [14]). Coating thicknesses between 1.5 and 5 μm were produced. The fibres coated with the graded titanium boride coatings (gTiB) were additionally coated with 30 μm of the IMI 834 alloy and tensile test samples were processed by HIPing.

Fig.5. Interfaces in composites with an additional gTiB coating a) after processing, b) after thermal treatment at 800°C/500h.

In Fig.5a the fibre-matrix interface is shown in composites with the additional gTiB coating. After composite processing the coating consists of two layers: the inner layer is TiB_2 , the outer TiB. Using EDX-line scan analysis [14] and analytical TEM [15] it can be shown that no reaction between the carbon coating of the SCS-6-fibre and the gTiB coating takes place and only a minor TiB-needle formation is observed at the interface after composite processing. As will be discussed below, no degradation of the tensile properties of the as-processed composites results due to the introduction of the additional gTiB coating.

The thermal stability of the fibre-matrix interface was determined by a thermal treatment of the composites at 800°C/500h. In Fig.5b the fibre-matrix interface is shown for the thermally treated composite. Using EDX-line scan analysis [14] and analytical TEM [15], the reaction between the gTiB coating and the carbon coating of the SCS-6 fibre and the IMI834 matrix was determined. The gTiB coating reacts with the carbon of the SCS-6 fibre under TiC formation. A TiC-layer forms adjoining to the carbon coating similar to the formation of reaction products in as-processed composites without the additional gTiB coating [15]. The gTiB-coating reacts with the IMI834 alloy also under TiC formation, the TiC at this interface is located not in a homogeneous layer but as a few micrometer large particles, Fig.5b. Details are discussed in [14,15].

TENSILE PROPERTIES

The rule of mixtures for ultimate tensile strength and Young's modulus can be considered as a rough criterion for a successful MMC processing. Using a ductile matrix as the Ti-6Al-4V-alloy, the fibre volume fraction determines the strength and modulus of the TMC's in agreement with that rule [1]. For the composites discussed in the present paper the tensile properties in the as-processed condition and after a thermal treatment at 800°C/500h are shown in Fig.6. After processing, the values of the

ultimate tensile strength, Fig. 6a, for the composites with the IMI834-alloy as matrix and with that matrix and an additional gTiB coating are in agreement with the predictions of the rule of mixtures and are comparable with those values obtained for the Ti-6Al-4V-alloy. The slight reaction of the gTiB-coating with the IMI834 alloy causes a negligible strength degradation of the composites. In composites with a more brittle matrix, as the super α_2 alloy (with a high oxygen content) and the γ -TiAl-alloy, the tensile experiments result in ultimate tensile strength values much lower than those predicted by the rule of mixtures. The deposition of the additional thin IMI 834 layer on the fibres for composites with the γ -TiAl, which was shown is preventing the crack formation during processing, does not result in any significant improvement of the tensile properties of the composites.

Fig. 6. Ultimate tensile strength a) and elongation at fracture b) for composites investigated in this paper.

After the heat treatment at 800°C/500h, only the tensile properties of the SiC-SCS-6 - IMI834 composites remain unchanged and their strength values are according to the predictions of the rule of mixtures. The reaction of the additional gTiB coating with the matrix results in a degradation of the composite strength. A decrease of the properties is also observed in SiC- γ -TiAl composites. Only the properties of the composites processed with the coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl - IMI834 remain also unchanged (at the lower values measured in the as-processed condition).

As is well known, Young's modulus is less sensitive to matrix properties and fibre matrix reaction. The values of the modulus for all composites are in the region between 180 and 230 GPa [16] and any significant effects of thermal treatment, fibre-matrix reaction and matrix properties are not observed, therefore. The elongation is again sensitive to these parameters, as can be seen from Fig. 6b. The effect of matrix ductility and thermal treatment on elongation is similar to that on the ultimate tensile strength. The highest elongation at fracture in TMC of 1.3 % is determined by the properties of the fibres. This value is measured for the composites with the ductile matrix Ti-6Al-4V, IMI834 and with a slight reduction also for the composites with the additional gTiB coating. The brittleness of super α_2 and γ -TiAl causes a decrease of the elongation in these composites.

After heat treatment, the elongation remains unchanged in composites with the IMI834 as matrix. Again similar to the strength, the elongation of the composites with the additional gTiB coating is

reduced due to the heat treatment at 800°C/500h, however. The elongation of composites with the coating system IMI834- γ -TiAl -IMI834 remains unchanged after thermal treatment at approximately 0.95 %.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

Using fibre coating and HIPing as a TMC processing method, the microstructure of composites can be designed according to the needs of consolidation during processing and the mechanical properties. A homogeneous chemical element concentration and a small grain size below 1 μm can be obtained using magnetron sputtering as the matrix deposition method. The small grain size allows to apply low temperatures and short HIPing times for the composite consolidation. For the super α_2 alloy 870°C was determined experimentally as the lowest consolidation temperature. For the consolidation of composites the number and the dimension of imperfections is important. Large imperfections, as they are still present in our composites before HIPing (Fig.2a), will increase the HIPing temperature needed for a complete consolidation. The HIPing temperature can be more decreased when the number and the dimensions of imperfections are lowered, therefore [17].

For matrix materials with low ductility at HIPing temperatures, as the γ -TiAl, the application of thin ductile layers as a "consolidation aid" can successfully reduce the HIPing temperature and time [17]. This was proved experimentally in this paper by applying the IMI834 alloy. The thickness of the additional IMI834 coating was not optimized in our case, however. A further decrease of the HIPing temperature and time should be possible.

The crack formation during the cooling process after processing in composites with the γ -TiAl alloy as matrix is caused by the difference in the thermal expansion coefficients of fibre and matrix and the brittleness of the matrix. In the fibre matrix interface residual stresses are forming during cooling [18]. For composites with a brittle matrix these stresses cause the formation of cracks as observed in Fig.4a. For the reduction of the stress concentration at the fibre-matrix interface the SiC-fibres were coated with a thin IMI834 alloy before the deposition of the γ -TiAl alloy. The thickness of the IMI834 layer was only 1.5 μm . According to [19], the thickness of a ductile layer should be 5 μm to prevent the crack formation. Layers of this thickness may also improve the tensile properties of the composites. This will be examined in future experiments.

The application of a consolidation aid is successful in preventing cracks during cooling of composites with a brittle matrix, as the γ -TiAl. During an application of composites at higher temperatures and also during processing, an interdiffusion of alloying elements of the consolidation aid and the brittle matrix takes place. For long-time thermal stability an alloy should be used as a "consolidation aid" in which this interdiffusion does not influence the mechanical properties of the composite.

The IMI834 alloy (and probably similar near α -alloys) presently appears to be the most successful matrix for composites with high-temperature applications. The tensile properties in the as-processed composites and for the composites thermally treated at 800°C/500h are according to the predictions of the rule of mixtures. From the point of view of matrix properties and due to the fibre matrix interaction, these composites cannot be applied at temperatures higher than roughly 600°C, however.

The concept of Knights [13] of a graded titanium boride (gTiB) coating as an additional diffusion and reaction barrier in SiC-Ti composites was realized using our magnetron sputtering equipment with two magnetron pairs. In the as-processed composites only a small interaction of the gTiB coating with the matrix is observed. The tensile properties are according to the predictions of the rule of mixture. At 800°C the gTiB coating reacts both with the carbon coating and with the titanium alloy under TiC formation. The reaction of the gTiB coating with the carbon coating of the SCS-6 fibre cannot be explained by thermodynamic considerations (TiB₂ is more stable than TiC [13]). The observed TiC formation at the interface between the gTiB coating and the matrix indicates that the

unsufficient thermal stability at 800°C is caused by the carbon and titanium diffusion through the gTiB coating [14,15].

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